

netWorked Youth Research for **Empowerment** in the Digital society

Inclusion Criteria

WP2_D2.1 v2

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Acronyms, Figures and Tables

Acronyms

D	Deliverable
ESCS	PISA index of Economic, Social and Cultural Status
HISEI	Highest International Socio Economic Index
ILO	International Labour Organisation
IOM	International Organisation for Migration
ISCED	International Classification of Education
ISEI	International Socio Economic Index
ISCO	International Standard Classification of Occupation
OECD	Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development
PISA	Programme for International Student Assessment
SES	Socioeconomic Status
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation
WP	Work Package

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Glossary of Terms

Culture

A social system of meaning and custom that is developed by a group of people. These groups are distinguished by a set of unspoken rules that shape values, beliefs, habits, patterns of thinking, behavior and styles of communication.

Disability

Physical or mental impairment, the perception of a physical or mental impairment, or a history of having had a physical or mental impairment that limits one or more major life activities.

Diversity

Psychological, physical, and social differences that occur among any and all individuals; including but not limited to race, ethnicity, nationality, religion, socioeconomic status, education, marital status, language, age, gender, sexual orientation, mental or physical ability, and learning styles. A diverse group, community, or organization is one in which a variety of social and cultural characteristics exist.

Diversity Management

A management model which describes the measures leading to acknowledgement and valuing of differences as well as regarded to be useful in an organization.

Equality

Evenly distributed access to resources and opportunity necessary for a safe and healthy life; uniform distribution of access to ensure fairness.

Ethnicity

Similarly to the term culture, an ethnic group or ethnicity is a category of people who identify with each other based on similarities such as common ancestral, language, social, cultural or national experiences.

Equity

The guarantee of fair treatment, access, opportunity, and advancement while at the same time striving to identify and eliminate barriers that have prevented the full participation of some groups. The principle of equity acknowledges that there are historically underserved and under-represented populations and that fairness regarding these unbalanced conditions is needed to assist equality in the provision of effective opportunities to all groups.

Gender

The socially constructed ideas about the behavior, actions and roles of a particular sex; differentiated from sex, a system of classification based on biological and physical differences, such as primary and secondary sexual characteristics.

Inclusion

Creation of environments in which any individual or group can be and feel welcomed, respected, supported, and valued, so as to be able to fully participate. An inclusive and welcoming climate embraces differences and offers respect in words and actions for all people.

Marginalization

The placement of minority groups and cultures outside mainstream society. All that varies from the norm of the dominant culture is devalued and at times perceived as deviant and regressive.

Migration

The movement of a person or a group of persons, either across an international border, or within a state. It includes the migration of refugees and displaced persons, economic migrants, and persons moving for other purposes, including family reunification.

Norm

An ideal standard that is binding upon the members of a group and serves to guide, control, or regulate power and acceptable behavior.

Stereotype

A positive or negative set of beliefs held by an individual about the characteristics of a certain group.

Sexual orientation

An enduring pattern of romantic or sexual attraction (or a combination of these) to persons of the opposite sex or gender, the same sex or gender, or to both sexes or more than one gender. These attractions are generally subsumed under heterosexuality, homosexuality and bisexuality while asexuality (the lack of sexual attraction to others) is sometimes identified as the fourth category.

Transgender

An umbrella term for people whose gender identity differs from their birth gender. Transgender can refer to a range of groups including transsexual people and those who see themselves as not clearly fitting into a male or female identity. Transgender people may or may not alter their bodies hormonally and/or surgically.

1 The WYRED Project

1.1 The Idea and the Aims

The emergence of the young as a distinct social group, and their slowly increasing empowerment through the availability of digital technology, has brought with it an understanding that they have a key role to play in the digital society, as drivers of new behaviours and understandings. However, their active participation in society is not reflected sufficiently in policy and decision-making, especially in relation to digital issues. Because of this, they are not well represented and their voices are unheard, and this makes it hard for research and policy to

identify and understand their needs. These issues are further complicated by the fact that the group of young people is a swiftly moving target, as heterogeneous as wider society, and its members may be unwilling to be subjects of research.

The WYRED project (netWorked Youth Research for Empowerment in the Digital society) (García-Peñalvo, 2016, 2017; García-Peñalvo & Kearney, 2016) aims to provide a framework for research in which children and young people can express and explore their perspectives and interests in relation to digital society, but also a platform from which they can communicate their perspectives to other stakeholders effectively through innovative engagement processes. WYRED will do this by implementing a generative research cycle involving networking, dialogue, participatory research and interpretation phases centred around and driven by children and young people, out of which a diverse range of outputs, critical perspectives and other insights will emerge to inform policy and decision-making in relation to children and young people's needs in relation to digital society.

The project is informed by the recognition that young people of all ages have the right to participation and engagement. It has a strong focus on inclusion, diversity and the empowerment of the marginalised. The aim is to replace the disempowering scrutiny of conventional research processes with the empowerment of self-scrutiny and self-organisation through social dialogue and participatory research (Griffiths et al., 2017).

1.2 The Process

The project work plan involves ten work packages (WP, see Figure 1). The first of these involves the definition of the different processes involved in the research cycle, and the second is dedicated to the preparation of the inclusion strategy and its implementation throughout the project, while the third focuses on the development of the WYRED platform, which will be used during the entire project as the space in which the activities and interaction take place, after the first three preparatory work packages have been completed.

Figure 1: WYRED work packages (WP)

The next five work packages cover the full cycle of activity in WYRED. This starts with network building in WP 4, in which the children and young people who will participate in the research cycle are attracted and engaged and the principal themes that represent their concerns are identified. The next work package (5) focuses on social dialogue around those themes, exploring them in order to identify key research questions relating to the digital society that concern children and young people. In the subsequent work package (6), these children and young people, supported by the partners, will focus on designing and implementing research activities to explore these questions and issues in a range of different ways. WP7 focuses on the interpretation and evaluation both of the process and its resulting production types by the young research participants and partners, and of different formats and artefacts that will be used to present the results, principally insights and recommendations to different target groups at policy level and in wider society. The final phase of the cycle in WP8 focuses on the dissemination and exploitation of these results, though this work package runs throughout the project, engaging in the valorization of the WYRED activity through workshops, event participation, online activity and association. These 5 work packages form a cycle that is aimed at generating insights relating to the perspectives and concerns of children and young people in relation to digital society. The cycle repeats twice during the funding period of the project and will continue indefinitely after the funding period under the aegis of the WYRED Association. The WYRED cycle is supported by 2 other work packages focusing on management (WP9) and quality (WP10).

The present report focusses on WP 2 and presents the activities of this work package within the first three months of the WYRED project.

2 Inclusion in WYRED

2.1 Work Package 2 - Inclusion

Inclusion in WYRED is committed to an understanding of diversity that regards differences as normal and values the idea of anyone equally participating in all aspects of life and decision-making. Focusing on the issue of giving the great variety of children and young people a voice- is one of the project's most essential prerequisites, both for the quality of the outcome and for fulfilling its objectives. The inclusion process is an integral part of the whole work process and it accompanies WYRED from the very beginning to even beyond the end of the project, as sustainability of the project will be closely related to the success of WYRED's theoretical understanding and practical implementation of inclusion. Inclusion criteria within the first project cycle are initially oriented towards internationally well-known diversity criteria (e.g. Abdul- Hussain & Baig, 2009), which will continuously be evaluated throughout the progress of the project. When, during the course of the project, it turns out to be necessary, these preliminary criteria will be adapted to the needs of WYRED.

As a sociological term, inclusion indicates a society in which every person is accepted and regarded as equal and self-determined, irrespective of specific individual diversity criteria. Differences between individuals are regarded as an enrichment, as normal. Inclusion is often defined in delineation from integration, which goes back to the 1970s (see figure 2). It was a response to the segregation of people with disability in education and society. Exclusion of handicapped persons, treatment in special institutions and a norm-oriented understanding of normality were radically questioned. The integration of children and adults with disability into regular school classes (supported by special-needs teachers), into society (supported by ambulant treatment) and into the labour market (supported by work assistants) we promoted, and self-determination became the leading paradigm. In the last 40 years, the term integration was especially used in education. Many different models were developed, ranging from the celebration of festivities together, to real integration into mainstream education whenever possible. (see e.g. Wikipedia: 'Soziale Inklusion')

Figure 2: From Segregation to Inclusion (source: self-designed according to: https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Soziale_Inklusion)

At the World Conference on Special Needs held by the UNESCO in 1994 the term inclusion – originally stemming from the USA – was introduced and spread worldwide (e.g. UNESCO, 1999). Whereas integration intends to integrate handicapped persons into society, inclusion goes farther: it focuses on changing existing structures and attitudes so that they regard the differences and diversity of all people as normal. Inclusion values the equality and equal participation of every member of society in all aspects of life, including civic, social, economic, and political activities, as well as in decision-making processes. Regarding difference as normal is the most essential proposition in the model of inclusion.

2.2 Inclusion Team

The WYRED inclusion team assures continuous exchange regarding diversity criteria (see below) as well as cultural and regional aspects of inclusion. All partners selected their representatives for the inclusion team, whose responsibility it is to assure diversity in WYRED and to continuously monitor the status quo of inclusion within the research circles. To ensure an ongoing reflection and/or adaptation of the preliminarily agreed criteria within this report, quarterly skype-meetings will be organized by the partner MOVES. These online meetings will bring together the partners' experiences with the implementation of diversity criteria in the ongoing research process within their respective countries. The meetings aim at continuously collecting feedback about the applicability of the criteria and about how far the predefined criteria and respective benchmarks have been reached. The protocols of the Skype meetings will report the actual inclusion status of WYRED in terms of participating children and youth and it will summarize the recommendations for the further process. The first online meeting, based on an agenda agreed by the inclusion team, will take place three months after the due date of Deliverable 2.1 (31.01.2017) in April 2017.

In Table 1, the inclusion team members of all partner organisations are presented.

Partner	Name	Country	Member
1	UNIVERSITY of SALAMANCA (USAL)	Spain	María José Rodríguez Conde
2	OXFAM	Italy	Federica Cical
3	PARTNERS for YOUTH EMPOWERMENT (PYE)	England	Anna Renau
4	ASIST OGRETIM KURUMLARI A. (DOGA)	Turkey	Sedef Altas
5	EARLY YEARS - THE ORGANISATION FOR YOUNG CHILDREN	Northern Ireland	Mary O'Reilly
6	YOUTH FOR EXCHANGE AND UNDERSTANDING INTERNATIONAL AISBL(YEU)	Belgium	Panagiotis Chatzimichail
7	MOVES - CENTRE for GENDER and DIVERSITY	Austria	Sabine Zauchner-Studnicka
8	THE BOUNDARIES OBSERVATORY C.I.C	England	Nick Kearney
9	TEL AVIV UNIVERSITY (TAU)	Israel	Tal Soffer

Table 1: WYRED Inclusion Team

Table 1 represents the broad variety of cultures in the WYRED Inclusion Team and the wealth of (technical) backgrounds the partners come from. Gender balance (3 men, 6 women) is sufficiently given in the composition of the entire WYRED team, which in January 2017 consists of 10 men and 14 women.

2.3 Deliverable 2.1 Objectives

The present deliverable is the first WP2 report about inclusion in WYRED, which will be followed by the yearly inclusion reports in month 12 (October 2017), month 24 (October 2018) and month 36 (October 2019). Based upon literature and data, Deliverable 2.1 proposes and defines the essential diversity factors to be implemented into the research process in a first step. The second main issue of the report is to operationalize these criteria for use in research. It is different to the following reports, in that it is more technically oriented, providing the partners with practical information about how to efficiently implement the individual criteria in their countries, which will form the main part of the present report. Further, the integration of partners' feedback is most essential for WYRED, as it not only adds culture-specific aspects to the diversity criteria, but also enhances the way of operationalizing them.

The process of defining inclusion, as well as selecting the diversity-criteria for WYRED, started collaboratively at the kick off-meeting in early November 2016, when MOVES put up a first set of criteria for discussion. The partners gave several valuable inputs, ranging from amending general factors like geographic location to allowing for different realities in the partner countries to follow differentiated ways of operationalization. Further, until the end of December 2016, the partners were offered the possibility of continuously adding to their comments to D 2.1 to the WP2 wiki at the WYRED (redmine) collaboration platform, and were asked to add their feedback to the draft in January.

The changes in the present version of D2.1 (v2) are derived from discussions at the 2nd project meeting in Vienna and continuous further exchanges between the partners regarding applicability and operationalization the

diversity criteria. This especially accounts for the diversity categories ethnic background and religion. D2.1_v2 presents the WYRED inclusion criteria as to be implemented on the platform, when the participants start their research and exploration processes.

3 Diversity Criteria

3.1 Diversity in WYRED

Diversity is referred to as the variety to be found in human beings, who differ from one another in many respects with the basic idea of anyone to be unique. Such a broad definition of diversity can mean anything and nothing, so that, in numerous approaches, diversity was connected to specific aspects, originally comprising gender and ethnicity, but also including – although not solely – other human differences, such as education, ethnicity, age, sexual orientation, social class, physical ability or attributes, religious or ethical values, national origin, or political beliefs (see also Figure 3). *“When trying to describe the variety and differences of individuals with specific characteristics the danger arises of reducing the complexity of the variety which makes humans unique to simple categories.”*¹ (Abdul- Hussain & Baig, 2009, p. 27). This means that focussing on these categories without considering the differences which also consist within the categories will lead to stereotypes, as Stuber and Achenbach (2004, p. 18) explain: *“A specific risk arises when selected criteria are reduced and when, simultaneously, difference in the sense of dichotomy and separation is emphasized.”*²

An understanding of diversity as the implementation of inclusion, as described in chapter 2, therefore needs reflection on these issues, especially when considering for example the recent discussions about immigration in Europe, which tends to emphasize the problematic aspects of diversity. In WYRED, diversity is regarded as valuable because the differences of backgrounds that characterize people lead to different perspectives, to different understandings of the world. Page (2007) regards diversity as the differences in the ways problem-solvers encode the problem and search for solutions, and states that *“in problem-solving, diversity is powerful stuff”* (p. xxvi). Especially for an increasingly complex and consistently changing digital society, this understanding of diversity shows a way to go about improving the world and creating an inclusive society that takes advantage of peoples’ diverse resources.

¹ German: “Bei dem Versuch, Vielfalt und Unterschiedlichkeit in Bezug auf die Individualität der Menschen mit konkreten Aspekten zu beschreiben, besteht die Gefahr, die Komplexität der vielfältigen Aspekte, die Menschen ausmacht und voneinander unterscheidet, zu reduzieren.“

² German: “Ein besonderes Risiko besteht in der Reduzierung der ausgewählten Unterscheidungsfaktoren bei gleichzeitiger Betonung von Unterschiedlichkeit im Sinne von (trennendem) Anderssein.“

When describing diversity, the chart by Loden and Rosener (1991) displayed in Figure 3 is often used and copied, be it in the form as shown, or adapted to e.g. national contexts, or to other (also more politically correct) languages. The so-called model of “Four Layers of Diversity” puts personality – which is understood as a unique combination of individual characteristics – at the centre. The primary (also internal) dimensions describe categories that cannot be influenced by ourselves³ and are regarded as the core dimensions of diversity. Secondary (also external) categories can be more or less changed, and shape personality like the primary dimensions.

Figure 3: Four Layers of Diversity, Diversity Criteria in WYRED (green)

Diversity is also a core economic topic, therefore dimensions making a difference on an organisational level are likewise defined. In this context, the concept of diversity management in organisations is to be mentioned as a management model which describes the measures leading to the acknowledgement and valuing of differences, as well as being something useful to an organisation in itself (Abdul- Hussain & Baig, 2009; Gardenswartz & Rowe, 2003; Stuber & Achenbach, 2004).

For WYRED especially the inner dimensions of diversity and some of the external dimensions (marked in green) are initially proposed to be implemented by the partners. These are:

1. Gender

³ Apart from hormonal or surgical alterations of transgender persons.

2. Age
3. Education and/or work situation
4. Socio-economic status
5. Geographic location
6. Cultural background/migration
7. Disabilities
8. Religion
9. Sexual orientation

Following the discussions at and after the 2nd project-meeting according to cultural applicability of the criteria, several options not to give answers were added to the questionnaire. Further, question 6 was divided into “Ethnic/national background” and “Migration” and or question 8 the issue of being an active part of a religious group was added. Therefore, the WYRED inclusion criteria for the present version, which is intended to be published on the platform, are:

1. Gender (2 versions according to age and/or country)
2. Age
3. Education or work situation
4. Socio-economic status
5. Geographic location
6. Migration
7. Ethnic/national background
8. Religion
9. Disabilities
10. Sexual orientation (implementation depending on age and/or country)

In the following pages, these criteria will be described in the form of a short (theoretical) introduction, the options for operationalization and the benchmarks the WYRED inclusion team will initially set itself.

3.2.1 Gender

3.2.1.1 Description/Background

The statement of Simone de Beauvoir "*One is not born, but rather becomes, a woman*" (2016, p. 267) goes along with the state-of-the-art gender theory of (de)constructivism, established by one of the most influential gender theorists and philosophers, Judith Butler (e.g. Butler 1991, 2004; Villa, 2010). It was she who introduced the theory of the social construction of gender. She differentiated between the biological (sex) and social aspect (gender), the latter being consistently constructed in interactions and discourses (Gildemeister, 2010; West & Fenstermaker, 1995). The term gender is understood as all characteristics, attributes, traits, and expectations or behaviour that are ascribed to being a ‘real’ woman or a ‘real’ man.

There is hardly a single social context, where gender dichotomies are not relevant. Even if a man and a woman behave exactly the same way, it is often differently evaluated. Although, as early as 1984, Carol Hagemann-White analysed the studies on gender differences available at that time and found no naturally given differences in ability upon which differences in behaviour could have been based. On the contrary, it turned out that women and men have a very similar "basic repertoire", but in daily life mainly gender specific aspects of this repertoire are used, motivated by a clear consciousness and a common understanding about what is appropriate for the genders. Just as gender stereotypes are socially constructed, so they can also be deconstructed. Reflection on a term's historical or genealogical development shows its basic openness to different meanings. This in turn facilitates changeability and deconstruction by means of irritation (Butler, 2004; Feustel, 2015).

3.2.1.2 Operationalization

The criterion Gender will be operationalized in two versions, to be chosen deliberately by the partners. One version reflects deconstructive openness in acknowledging transitions between the gender-dichotomies (e.g. transgender persons), the other represents the established and frequently used form of clearly distinguishing between the genders.

Question 1 (Q1): Which gender do you attribute to yourself?

Version 1

female

male

Version 2

female

male

not mentioned above (if you wish, please specify): _____

no answer

3.2.1.3 Benchmark

WYRED aims at an equal share of male and female participants and is open to diversity in also considering possible further gender categories.

3.2.2 Age

3.2.2.1 Description/Background

According to the recent European Report on being young in Europe today (Statistical Office of the European Communities, 2015), children are defined as being younger than 15 years old and young people are defined as being younger than 30 years old. The main target group of WYRED therefore covers a very broad age spectrum. It is not only that children and young people – as stated in the

proposal – are a constantly moving target, but also that the variety of their ages reflects a high diversity of values, needs and ideas.

3.2.2.2 Operationalisation

Question 2 (Q2): Your year of birth:

→ List starting with 1945

3.2.2.3 Benchmark

WYRED aims at reaching participants from all the age groups listed below:

1. Younger than 10 years old,
2. 10 to 14 years old,
3. 15 to 19 years old,
4. 20 to 24 years old and
5. 25 to 29 years old.

It is obvious that reaching a balanced distribution of all groups will be challenging within the single partner countries, since it is not only the case that the different target groups need to be reached, but also that these groups demand different expertise when thinking of implementing the research cycles. For example, the moderation of the exploration processes of young children will demand other approaches and expertise than that for university students or for apprentices. This also accounts for other diversity criteria (e.g. educational level, disabilities), but is most visible here. Nonetheless, even in this initial phase, the consortium in general aims at a balanced distribution of the age groups, facilitated by the expertise of the partner organisations. Supported by the continuous extensions of the networks throughout the research process, new or other options of cooperation in the single partner countries will further be supportive of this aim.

3.2.3 Educational and Work Background

3.2.3.1 Description|Background

ISCED (International Standard Classification of Education) is the educational classification of the UNESCO (United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organisation). National education systems vary in terms of structure and curricular content. It is therefore difficult to compare systems across countries, as will be necessary in WYRED. In order to understand and properly interpret the processes of education systems from a global perspective, it is vital to ensure that the data is comparable. This can be done by applying the International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED), the standard framework used to categorise and report education statistics that are comparable cross-nationally.

For every WYRED partner country, the 2011 Operation Manual (UNESCO, 2015) provides detailed information on how to integrate their respective national school levels into the ISCED framework, the details of which are as follows:

1. ISCED 0 – Pre-Primary Level of Education,
2. ISCED 1 – Primary Level of Education
3. ISCED 2 – Lower Secondary Level of Education
4. ISCED 3 – Upper Secondary Level of Education
5. ISCED 4 – Post-Secondary Non-Tertiary
6. ISCED 5 – Short-cycle tertiary education
7. ISCED 6 – Bachelor’s or equivalent level
8. ISCED 7 – Master’s or equivalent level
9. ISCED 8 – Doctoral or equivalent level

But it is also the young working person – being employed, self-employed or unemployed, being an apprentice or a skilled worker – who is an essential target group for WYRED.

3.2.3.2 Operationalisation

Question 3 (Q3): At the moment, are you a student in formal education?

o If yes:

Which form of education/school type? [insert national categories, then add to ISCED levels]

o If not:

What is your highest level of education? [insert national categories, then add to ISCED levels]

What are you doing in the moment? List to be chosen:

o Non-formal training

o Internship

o Employed

o Self-employed

o Unemployed

3.2.3.3 Benchmark

As with the age groups (see 3.3.2), a balanced distribution of educational levels and of youth in the workforce is aimed at.

3.2.4 Socio-economic status

3.2.4.1 Description|Background

“Socioeconomic status (SES) is an economic and sociologically combined total measure of an individual's or family's economic and social position in relation to others, based on income, education, and occupation. [...] Socioeconomic status is typically broken into high, middle, and low SES to describe the three areas a family or an individual may fall into. When placing a family or individual into one of these categories, any or all of the three variables (income, education, and occupation) can be assessed.” (Wikipedia)

When assessing the socio-economic status of children and young people, an indicator derived from the parents' income, education and occupation is often criticized due to the lack of reliability of the data – especially regarding income and the specific occupational status of the parents. Therefore, also other – indirect – indicators are often implemented. One indicator often applied is “home resources”, which may, for example, be the number of books in the student's home, an indicator being in agreement with Bourdieu's theory of cultural capital (Bourdieu, 1986; Bourdieu & Kreckel, 1983) as a marker for (un)privileged families.

Of course, indicators derived from multiple measures tend to be more reliable and have e.g. stronger correlations with school achievement than single measures. In the OECD Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), a student's socio-economic status is estimated by the PISA index of economic, social and cultural status (ESCS), which is derived from several variables related to students' family background: parents' education, parents' occupations, a number of home possessions that can be taken as proxies for material wealth, and the number of books and other educational resources available in the home (OECD, 2014; OECD iLibrary, 2016).

In order to assure ease of use as far as possible, in WYRED solely the parental education according to ISCED (see above) will be used. The number of books in the household will not be considered, as in many families online-readers replace hard-cover versions of books. Students may be classified as socio-economically advantaged if they are among the 25% of students with the highest parental' values on the index, and are regarded as socio-economically disadvantaged if their values are among the lowest 25% within their country. Students whose values are in the middle 50% within their country are classified as having an average socio-economic status.

3.2.4.2 Operationalisation

Question 4 (Q4): Parents' educational status

o What is the highest school level attained by your mother? → ISCED List

o I can't answer this question

o What is the highest school level attained by your father? → ISCED List

o I can't answer this question

3.2.4.3 Benchmark

A share of high (25%), middle (50%) and low (25%) SES per county is envisaged.

3.2.5 Geographic Location

3.2.5.1 Description|Background

Geographic location makes a difference. This may account for differences in the availability of educational (Ortlieb & Cheek, 2008) or health systems (e.g. Chan, Hart, & Goodman, 2006) in the countryside and in smaller or bigger towns. It also may account for the development of technological infrastructure, such as broadband internet access (Whitacre & Mills, 2007), or the expansion of public transport or the road network. Moreover, the development of ventures may, for example, differ in relation to the geographic location (e.g. Fernhaber, Gilbert, & McDougall, 2008).

3.2.5.2 Operationalisation

Question 5 (Q5):

Where do you live? → List

- village/rural community (< 5,000 inhabitants)
- small town (5,000-20,000 inhabitants)
- medium town (20,000-100,000 inhabitants)
- big town (> 100,000 inhabitants)

Where do you go to school or to work? → List

- village/rural community (< 5,000 inhabitants)
- small town (5,000-20,000 inhabitants)
- medium town (20,000-100,000 inhabitants)
- big town (> 100,000 inhabitants)

[categories according to BBSR, 2016/Germany]

3.2.5.3 Benchmark

Representation in relation to the national population in the four categories is aspired to.

3.2.6 Migration

3.2.6.1 Description|Background

Migration is defined as *"The movement of a person or a group of persons, either across an international border, or within a state. It is a population movement, encompassing any kind of movement of people,*

whatever its length, composition and causes; it includes migration of refugees, displaced persons, economic migrants, and persons moving for other purposes, including family reunification" (IOM, 2011).

For the operationalisation of migration, questions as being asked in PISA 2012 (OECD, 2014) will be used.

3.2.6.2 Operationalisation

Question 6 (Q6):

- o Which language is mainly spoken in your family? (open question)
- o Where were you born? List with countries: e.g.:
http://www.nationsonline.org/oneworld/countries_of_the_world.htm - (also available in Spanish, German, Italian)
- o Where was your father born? → List
 - o I can't answer this question
- o Where was your mother born? → List
 - o I can't answer this question

3.2.6.3 Benchmark

Individual estimation of the share of migrants in the partner countries,

3.2.7 Ethnic/National Background

3.2.7.1 Description|Background

Wikipedia defines an ethnic group as follows: *"An ethnic group or ethnicity is a category of people who identify with each other based on similarities such as common ancestral, language, social, cultural or national experiences. Ethnicity is often an inherited status based on the society in which one lives. (...)"* (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ethnic_group).

This concept is closely related to the definition of culture. However, it is to be clearly distinguished from the term race, which refers to the concept of dividing people into groups based on their physical characteristics (see e.g. http://www.diffen.com/difference/Ethnicity_vs_Race).

Question 7 (Q7):

What is your ethnic/national background* like for example, Kurd, Romani, Catalan, French, Austrian Croat, Walloon, Persian, Dutch)?

(open question)

- o No answer

* Might be added: An ethnic or national group is a group of people sharing for example a common language, cultural heritage, social or national experiences.

The examples used for ethnic/national groups can be adapted to the partners conditions.

[3.2.7.2 Benchmark](#)

Specific ethnic groups in the partner countries, as far as they are given.

3.2.8 Religion

[3.2.8.1 Description|Background](#)

According to Wikipedia, the following major religions exist worldwide: Christianity, with about 2,3 billion adherents; Islam, with about 1,6 billion adherents; Hinduism, with about 940 million adherents; Buddhism, with about 460 million adherents; and Judaism, with about 15 million adherents.

[3.2.8.2 Operationalisation](#)

Question 8 (Q8)

o *What is your religious background like for example, Christian (Protestant, Catholic), Muslime (Sunnite, Shiite), Jew?*

(open question)

No answer

o *Do you consider yourself an active part of this group?*

Yes

No

No answer

[3.2.8.3 Benchmark](#)

Share as related to the partner countries.

3.2.9 Disabilities

[3.2.9.1 Description|Background](#)

There are 80 million Europeans with disabilities. This is over 15% of the whole population. At present, there exists no unique and agreed definition of disability which relates to a different understanding of disability within the main models. While the medical model is based on the persons' "impairment" and "lack of ability", the social model shifts the focus onto "disability" due to surrounding barriers. In the social model, disability is understood as the result of the interaction between the individual's impairment and the barriers created by society, whether they are social, environmental or attitudinal (see e.g. Shakespeare, 2013).

The main types of disabilities are: (1) Physical disability – a condition that limits one or more basic physical activities, (2) Sensory disability – a condition affecting one of the five senses, typically vision, hearing, or touch, (3) Mental disability – mental health disabilities can take many forms, such as e.g. schizophrenia, mood disorders, anxiety disorders, eating disorders, personality disorders or organic brain disorders (e.g., Alzheimer’s, a stroke, dementia) (4) Cognitive disability – an impairment that affects an individual’s ability to access, process, or remember information, and (5) Learning disability – a learning disability is essentially a specific and persistent disorder of a person’s central nervous system affecting the learning process. This impacts a person’s ability to either interpret what they see and hear, or to link information from different parts of the brain. (see e.g. Wikipedia, People First).

[3.2.9.2 Operationalisation](#)

Question 9 (Q9):

Do you have any long-term illness, health problem or disability which limits your daily activities?

No

Yes

No answer

[3.2.9.3 Benchmark](#)

A share of 15% of participants is aimed at.

[3.2.10 Sexual orientation](#)

[3.2.10.1 Description|Background](#)

Sexual orientation is an enduring pattern of romantic or sexual attraction (or a combination of these) to persons of the opposite sex or gender, the same sex or gender, or to both sexes or more than one gender. These attractions are generally subsumed under heterosexuality, homosexuality and bisexuality, while asexuality (the lack of sexual attraction to others) is sometimes identified as the fourth category (source: Wikipedia)

Similar to the operationalisation of gender, this criterion will be implemented when the participant has come of age and it is culturally viable in the partner countries.

[3.2.10.2 Operationalisation](#)

Question 10: Do you perceive yourself as being...

heterosexual?

homosexual?

- bisexual?
- no answer

[3.2.10.3 Benchmark](#)

The demographics of sexual orientation vary significantly, the most common ranges differ from 1 to 10%. Therefore, the benchmarks for this criterion may be within this range.

2 Further procedure

Based upon the present deliverable, diversity criteria – representing the “practical side” of inclusion – will be incorporated into the national research cycles. This means that all participants will be asked the questions specified and operationalised in chapter 3 of the present deliverable (for an overview see Annex 1). There are two questions which will need individual adaptation by the partners, i.e. the operationalisation of “Gender” and the use of the criterion “Sexual Orientation” in dependence on applicability in the partner-countries and/or the participant’s age.

The lively discussions beginning with and after the 2nd project meeting as well as the process of translation into the partner languages lead to this v2-document, in which the inclusion questions as thoroughly elaborated by all partners, are presented. As different as the inclusion criteria are, their operationalisation by the partners will be. It was a common decision of the consortium to start the implementation with the beginning of the research phase, as soon as the platform is available. The further processes will show, if the criteria work well as they are now or still will need to be adapted.

The implementation of the criteria in the partner countries is preceded by the Training Activities developed in D4.5, which are closely related to the Participant Protection Policy developed in work package 1 (D1.4). Therefore, in line with the participants’ decisions to enter the project, accompanied by age-adequate informed consents, they will be informed about the ethical issues in WYRED, which are e.g. to have the right not to answer questions, to stop participation at any time, to know how their personal data will be treated within the project, and to be informed about the WYRED open-access strategy. Being demographic personal data as specified in D1.4, inclusion criteria will be collected within the registration form on the WYRED platform. They will be stored in an off-line database, to which only the coordinating partner will have access, for the purpose of providing anonymous data regarding the demographics of participation. This means that also those participants who do not intend to explore their research topics online, or cannot do so, will fill in demographic data (though not necessarily creating a digital avatar) in the online registration form, either individually or supported by the researchers, teachers, youth workers, or legal representatives.

MOVES as the leader of WP2 is responsible for steadily collecting partners' feedback on the ongoing processes of inclusion and the applicability of the criteria, for providing and discussing solutions in problematic situations and keeping up to the benchmarks as specified before.

Practically, this is assured by quarterly online meetings of the inclusion team, depending upon the demographics analysed anonymously by the coordinator for the individual partner countries and the consortium as a whole. These participant demographics will be provided to all partners, in good time, before the online meetings. As stated before, a main aim – besides the status-quo of criteria implementation – is to bring together and to exchange the individual experiences of the partners. Beyond the background of the WYRED understanding of inclusion, which essentially entails the equality, self-determination and participation of all children and young people, these experiences will be reflected and discussed. In case of problems, these discussions and reflections will methodologically adopt a solution-oriented approach and its tools, as applied in systemic-constructivist business coaching (e.g. De Shazer & Berg, 2008; Furman, 2008; Hargens, 2011; Hargens & Grau, 1990).

The first "online" meeting of the inclusion team was replaced by a face-to-face discussion at the meeting in Vienna in May. The second online meeting is scheduled for September, both being the basis for the first inclusion report, which will be available in the end of October 2017.

3 References

3.1 Academic literature

- Abdul- Hussain, S., & Baig, S. (2009). *Diversity in Supervision, Coaching und Beratung*. Vienna: Facultas Verlags- und Buchhandels AG.
- BBSR, B. für B., - Stadt- und Raumforschung. (2016). Stadt- und Gemeindetypen. Source: http://www.bbsr.bund.de/BBSR/DE/Raumb Beobachtung/Raumabgrenzungen/StadtGemeindetyp/StadtGemeindetyp_node.html
- Beauvoir, S. de. (2016). *Das andere Geschlecht: Sitte und Sexus der Frau*. (U. Aumüller & G. Osterwald, Übers.) (15. Auflage). Reinbek bei Hamburg: Rowohlt Taschenbuch Verlag.
- Bourdieu, P. (1986). The Forms of Capital. Source: <https://www.marxists.org/reference/subject/philosophy/works/fr/bourdieu-forms-capital.htm>
- Bourdieu, P., & Kreckel, R. (1983). Ökonomisches Kapital, kulturelles Kapital, soziales Kapital. In *Soziale Ungleichheiten (Soziale Welt, Sonderheft 2)* (p. 183–198). Göttingen: Otto Schartz & Co.
- Butler, J. (1991). *Das Unbehagen der Geschlechter*. Frankfurt am Main: Suhrkamp.
- Butler, J. (2004). *Undoing Gender*. New York: Routledge.
- Chan, L., Hart, L. G., & Goodman, D. C. (2006). Geographic Access to Health Care for Rural Medicare Beneficiaries. *The Journal of Rural Health*, 22(2), 140–146. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1748-0361.2006.00022.x>
- De Shazer, S., & Berg, I. K. (2008). *Lösungen (er-)finden. Das Werkstattbuch der lösungsorientierten Kurztherapie* (6th edition). Dortmund: Verlag Modernes Lernen.
- Fernhaber, S. A., Gilbert, B. A., & McDougall, P. P. (2008). International Entrepreneurship and Geographic Location: An Empirical Examination of New Venture Internationalization. *Scholarship and Professional Work, Paper 94*. Abgerufen von http://digitalcommons.butler.edu/cob_papers/94?utm_source=digitalcommons.butler.edu%2Fcob_papers%2F94&utm_medium=PDF&utm_campaign=PDFCoverPages
- Feustel, R. (2015). *Die Kunst des Verschiebens. Dekonstruktion für Einsteiger*. Paderborn: Wilhelm Fink.
- Furman, B. (2008). *Es ist nie zu spät, eine glückliche Kindheit zu haben* (6th edition). Basel: Borgmann.
- Ganzeboom, H. B. ., De Graaf, P. ., & Treiman, D. J. (1992). : A Standard International Socio-Economic Index of Occupational Status. *Social Science Research* 21 (1), 1-56., 21(1), 1–56.
- Ganzeboom, H. G. B., & Treiman, D. D. J. (2003). Three Internationally Standardised Measures for Comparative Research on Occupational Status. In J. H. . Hoffmeyer-Zlotnik & C. Wolf (Hrsg.), *Advances in Cross-National Comparison: A European Working Book for Demographic and Socio-Economic Variables* (p. 159–193). New York.: Kluwer Academic Press.
- García-Peñalvo, F. J. (2016). The WYRED Project: A Technological Platform for a Generative Research and Dialogue about Youth Perspectives and Interests in Digital Society. *Journal of Information Technology Research*, 9(4), vi-x.

- García-Peñalvo, F. J. (2017). WYRED Project. *Education in the Knowledge Society*, 18(3), 7-14.
doi:10.14201/eks2017183714
- García-Peñalvo, F. J., & Kearney, N. A. (2016). Networked youth research for empowerment in digital society. The WYRED project. In F. J. García-Peñalvo (Ed.), *Proceedings of the Fourth International Conference on Technological Ecosystems for Enhancing Multiculturality (TEEM'16) (Salamanca, Spain, November 2-4, 2016)* (pp. 3-9). New York, NY, USA: ACM.
- Griffiths, D., Kearney, N. A., García-Peñalvo, F. J., Seoane-Pardo, A. M., Cicala, F., Gojkovic, T., . . . Zauchner-Studnicka, S. (2017). *Children and Young People Today: Initial Insights from the WYRED Project*. European Union: WYRED Consortium. Retrieved from <http://repositorio.grial.eu/handle/grial/990>.
doi:10.5281/zenodo.996356
- Gardenswartz, L., & Rowe, A. (2003). *Diverse teams at work: capitalizing on the power of diversity*. Alexandria, Va: Society for Human Resource Management.
- Gildemeister, R. (2010). Doing Gender: Soziale Praktiken der Geschlechtsunterscheidung. In R. Becker & B. Kortendieck (Hrsg.), *Handbuch der Frauen und Geschlechterforschung* (3rd edition, vol. 35, p. 137–145). Wiesbaden: VS Verlag.
- Hagemann-White, C. (1984). *Sozialisation: Weiblich - Männlich?* Opladen: Leske und Budrich.
- Hargens, J. (2011). *Bitte nicht helfen! Es ist auch schon so schwer genug*. (8th edition). Heidelberg: Carl-Auer.
- Hargens, J., & Grau, U. (1990). Kooperieren, reflektieren, öffentlich machen. Skizze eines systemischen Ansatzes auf konstruktivistischer Basis., 4(2), 151–155.
- International Labour Organisation. (2007). Resolution Concerning Updating the International Standard Classification of Occupations - ISCO-08.
Source:<http://www.ilo.org/public/english/bureau/stat/isco/docs/resol08.pdf>
- IOM, I. O. for M. (2011). , Glossary on Migration, International Migration Law Series No. 25, 2011. Abgerufen von <https://www.iom.int/key-migration-terms>
- Loden, M., & Rosener, J. B. (1991). *Workforce America!: managing employee diversity as a vital resource*. Homewood, Ill: Business One Irwin.
- OECD. (2014). *PISA 2012 Technical Report*. Source: <http://www.oecd.org/pisa/pisaproducts/PISA-2012-technical-report-final.pdf>
- OECD iLibrary. (2016). *PISA 2015 results*. Source: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/9789264266490-en>
- Ortlieb, E. R., & Cheek, E. H. (2008). How Geographic Location Plays a Role within Instruction: Venturing into both Rural and Urban Elementary Schools. *Educational Research Quarterly*, Sep., 48–64.
- Page, S. E. (2007). *The difference: how the power of diversity creates better groups, firms, schools, and societies* (3rd printing, 1st pbk. printing). Princeton, NJ: Princeton Univ. Press.
- Shakespeare, T. (2013). The Social Model of Disability. In L. J. Davis (ed.), *The disability studies reader* (4th ed, p. 214–221). New York, NY: Routledge.
- Statistical Office of the European Communities. (2015). *Being young in Europe today: 2015 edition*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. Source: <http://dx.publications.europa.eu/10.2785/59267>

- Stuber, M., & Achenbach, S. (2004). *Diversity: das Potenzial von Vielfalt nutzen - den Erfolg durch Offenheit steigern*. Neuwied: Luchterhand.
- UNESCO. (1999). A review of UNESCO Activities in the Light of the Salamanca Statement and Framework for Action.
- UNESCO. (2002). Records of the General Conference. Volume 1 Resolutions. Source: <http://unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0012/001246/124687e.pdf#page=67>
- UNESCO (ed.). (2015). *ISCED 2011 operational manual: guidelines for classifying national education programmes and related qualifications*. Paris: OECD.
- Villa, P.-I. (2010). (De)Konstruktion und Diskurs-Genealogie: Zur Position und Rezeption von Judith Butler. In R. Becker & B. Kortendieck (Hrsg.), *Handbuch Frauen- und Geschlechterforschung: Theorie, Methoden, Empirie* (3rd edition, p. 146–157). Wiesbaden: VS Verl. für Sozialwissenschaften.
- West, C., & Fenstermaker, S. (1995). Doing Difference. *Gender and Society*, 9(1), 8–37.
- Whitacre, B. E., & Mills, B. F. (2007). Infrastructure and the Rural—urban Divide in High-speed Residential Internet Access. *International Regional Science Review*, 30(3), 249–273.

3.2 Weblinks

- 'People First: 6 General Types of Disabilities', retrieved from <http://www.peoplefirst4aoda.com/6-general-types-of-disabilities/> [14.01.2017]
- Wikipedia, 'Disability', retrieved from: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Disability> [15.01.2017]
- Wikipedia, 'Sexual Orientation', retrieved from: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sexual_orientation [15.12.2016]
- Wikipedia, 'Socio-economic status', retrieved from: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Socioeconomic_status [15.01.2017]
- Wikipedia, 'Soziale Inklusion', retrieved from https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Soziale_Inklusion [13.10.2016]
- Wikipedia, 'Weltreligion', retrieved from: <https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Weltreligion> [15.10.2016]

4 Annex

4.1 Annex 1 – List of Questions_v2

Dear participant,

in empowering children and young people to get heard in the digital society a core aim of the WYRED project is to include a broad range of different voices, ideas and opinions into the project. We regard diverse perspectives to be a most valuable resource in dealing with (future) societal changes or digital developments. Therefore, in the following we ask you to answer some questions which focus on diversity and inclusion.

Q1 GENDER

Which gender do you attribute to yourself?

Version 1

female

male

Version 2 (If applicable: depending on country, participant's age)

female

male

not mentioned above (if you wish, please specify):

no answer

Q2 AGE

Your year of birth:

→ List starting with 1945

Q3 EDUCATIONAL or WORK BACKGROUND

At the moment, are you student in formal education?

o If Yes: → List ISCED

o If No:

What is your highest level of education? → List ISCED

What are you doing in the moment? → List

- o non-formal training,
- o internship,
- o employed,
- o self-employed,
- o unemployed

Q4 SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS

Parents' Educational Status

What is the highest school level attained by your mother? → List ISCED

- o *I can't answer this question*

What is the highest school level attained by your father? → List ISCED

- o *I can't answer this question*

Q5 GEOGRAPHIC LOCATION

Where do you live?

→ List

- o *Village/rural community (< 5,000 inhabitants)*
- o *Small town (5,000-20,000 inhabitants)*
- o *Medium town (20,000-100,000 inhabitants)*
- o *Big town (> 100,000 inhabitants)*

Where do you study or work?

→ List

- o *Village/rural community (< 5,000 inhabitants)*
- o *Small town (5,000-20,000 inhabitants)*
- o *Medium town (20,000-100,000 inhabitants)*
- o *Big town (> 100,000 inhabitants)*

Q6 MIGRATION

Which language is mainly spoken in your family?

→ (open question)

Where were you born?

→ List with countries: e.g.: http://www.nationsonline.org/oneworld/countries_of_the_world.htm - (also available in Spanish, German, Italian)

Where was your father born?

→ List

○ *I can't answer this question*

Where was your mother born?

→ List

○ *I can't answer this question*

Q7 ETHNIC/NATIONAL BACKGROUND

What is your ethnic/national background* like for example, Kurd, Romani, Catalan, French, Austrian Croat, Walloon, Persian, Dutch)?

(open question)

○ No answer

* Might be added: An ethnic or national group is a group of people sharing for example a common language, cultural heritage, social or national experiences.

The examples used for ethnic/national groups can be adapted to the partners' conditions.

Q8 RELIGIOUS BACKGROUND

What is your religious background like for example, Christian (Protestant, Catholic), Muslime (Sunnite, Shiite), Jew?

(open question)

○ No answer

Do you consider yourself an active part of this group?

- Yes
- No
- No answer

Q9 DISABILITY

Do you have any long-term illness, health problem or disability which limits your daily activities?

- No
- Yes
- No answer

Q10: SEXUAL ORIENTATION

If applicable: (depending on country, participant's age)

Do you perceive yourself as being ...

- List
- Heterosexual?
 - Homosexual?
 - Bisexual?
 - No answer

THANK YOU!